

Guidelines regarding Privacy issues for Institutional and Learning analytics to measure Digital Readiness

G1. Identify which personal data of users in your institution is affected by the analysis of digital readiness-related indicators.

G2. Data Minimization. For each indicator that requires personal data: collect and process only the minimum amount of personal data necessary for evaluating the digital readiness of the institution. Avoid collecting excessive or unnecessary personal information.

G3. Anonymization and Pseudonymization: Where possible, utilize anonymized or pseudonymized data during the assessment process. This helps protect individuals' identities and enhances privacy.

G4. Data Security: Implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to safeguard the collected data. Ensure secure storage, transfer, and handling of the data to prevent unauthorized access, loss, or disclosure.

G5. Data Retention: Establish a clear data retention policy and retain personal data only for as long as necessary to achieve the purpose for which it was collected. Once the data is no longer needed, securely dispose of it in accordance with applicable data protection regulations.

G6. Make sure these personal data used for digital readiness are processed in a lawful manner by the HEI, for either of these two alternatives:

- A) because your HEI can apply to “legitimate purpose” or B) because your HEI has enabled informed consent by the users

G7. In case the personal data are processed under “legitimate purpose”, add these data to the Data Protection Impact Assessment carried out by the HEI.

G8. Ensure that the data protection strategies in place in your HEI include the data used to calculate the DR indicators.

G9. Ensure that, when applicable, these data used to compute DR are also considered under the Data Subject Access Requests in place.

G10. In case the entity that uses the personal data is not the HEI itself (the DigiReady+ consortium or the institution that manages the DigiReady+ system when the project is over), you should create a Data Processing Agreement (DPA) with any party that acts as data processor.

G11. Regularly update your DPA. As certain procedures in your handling of personal data change over time, or other developments that impact existing agreements occur, it is crucial that your institution makes the individuals whose data are involved in the processing aware of this fact.